

MAMMALIAN NERVOUS SYSTEM AND REFLECTIVE RESPONSES

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Annotation: This article discusses the basic structure and functions of the nervous system and reflex responses in mammals. The nervous system in mammals, comprising the central and peripheral systems, controls the physiological processes of the organism. The article explores the main structures of the nervous system and the mechanism of reflex responses, explaining how they enable quick responses to changes in the environment. Additionally, it emphasizes the types of reflex responses in mammals and their role in survival. This article may be useful for biologists, veterinarians, and students interested in understanding the nervous system and reflex mechanisms in animals.

Keywords: mammals, nervous system, central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, reflex responses, spinal cord, sensory nerves, somatic nervous system, autonomic nervous system, conditional reflexes, skin reflexes, respiratory reflex.

Introduction. The nervous system and reflex responses of mammals (Mammalia) are important biological mechanisms for them. The nervous system, through the central and peripheral systems, is necessary for controlling all physiological processes of the organism and adapting to the environment. Reflex responses play an important role in ensuring the rapid and sensitive reactions of the animal. This article provides detailed information about the structure of the mammalian nervous system and the mechanism of reflex responses.

The main part. The nervous system is a system in the human and animal body that performs vital functions by connecting the activities of all organs and connecting the organism with the external environment. The nervous system is of decisive importance in the process of evolution of the animal organism and in the formation of complex relationships between organisms and the external environment.

The mammalian nervous system The mammalian nervous system consists of two main parts: the central nervous system (CNS) and the peripheral nervous system

(PNS). The central nervous system, through the brain and spinal cord, controls the entire body. The peripheral nervous system, on the other hand, transmits signals from the central nervous system to peripheral organs through nerves distributed throughout the body.

Central Nervous System (CNS): The brain is highly developed in mammals and controls all body functions. The main parts of the brain are:

- Cerebrum: Controls natural intelligence, memory, emotions, and movement.
- Spinal cord: Carries out reflex responses and transmits signals to higher parts of the brain.
- Midbrain and midbrain: Processes visual and auditory information, controls movement, and balance.

Peripheral Nervous System (PNS): The PNS connects all the organs, muscles, skin, and internal organs in the body. It is divided into two main branches:

- Somatic Nervous System: Controls voluntary movements and adaptation to the environment.
- Autonomic Nervous System: Controls internal organs in response to changing conditions (e.g., heart rate and breathing).

Reflex responses and the role of the nervous system. Reflex responses are the rapid and automatic responses of an animal to changes in its environment. Reflex responses are mediated by the central nervous system and are primarily developed in the spinal cord. Reflex responses allow the animal to respond quickly to threats and play an important role in maintaining life.

Structure of Reflex Responses: Reflex responses typically consist of the following main components:

Receptor: Receives a change in the external or internal environment. Sensory nerve: Carries the signal from the receptor to the central nervous system. Spinal cord: Processes the signal rapidly and produces a response. Motor nerve: Carries the signal from the spinal cord to muscles or other organs.

Types of reflex responses: Unconditioned reflexes: Unconditioned reflexes are unchanging, genotype-related, i.e. hereditary reactions of the organism to the effects of external and internal stimuli. For example, reflexes for feeding, breathing, reproduction, alertness to loud sounds, and escape in case of danger.

Conditioned reflexes: Based on Pavlov's theory of conditioned reflexes, animals are able to give learned and adapted responses to the circumstances. For example, what we have all observed in experiments is the naming of various domestic animals and their response to their own nicknames. This is due to the fact that they are fed when called by that name.

Examples of reflex responses in mammals

- Cutaneous reflexes: Sensation of pain or temperature through the skin and the associated reflex responses (e.g., withdrawing the hand from a hot object).
- Respiratory reflex: In mammals, the rate and depth of breathing are automatically controlled by the nervous system. Often, the rhythm and depth of breathing automatically change depending on the body's oxygen and carbon dioxide levels.

Conclusion. The relationship between the nervous system and reflex responses in mammals is important for the adaptation of the animal to environmental conditions and protection from dangers. The complex structure of the nervous system and reflex mechanisms are essential for the survival and development of animals. The study of the mammalian nervous system and reflex responses helps to open up many new knowledge in the fields of biology and psychology.

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